

Using Gamified Vocabulary Instruction to Enhance Young Learners' Motivation in English Learning at a Foreign Language Center in Ca Mau

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the effects of gamified vocabulary instruction on the motivation of young EFL learners at a foreign language center in Ca Mau, Vietnam. Although vocabulary learning is essential in EFL contexts, instructional practices in many Vietnamese language centers continue to rely heavily on repetition, translation, and rote memorization, which often fail to sustain learners' motivation. To address this issue, a ten-week gamified instructional program was implemented, integrating game elements such as points, badges, leaderboards, and collaborative activities into vocabulary lessons. Data were collected through a post-intervention questionnaire measuring learners' enjoyment, engagement, effort, and perceived usefulness of the activities, supplemented by semi-structured interviews to gain qualitative insights into learners' experiences. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were thematically analyzed to identify recurring motivational patterns. The study aims to provide empirical evidence on the motivational impact of gamified vocabulary instruction and to contribute to the limited research on gamification in provincial EFL contexts in Vietnam. The findings are expected to offer practical implications for language teachers and institutions seeking to enhance learner motivation through more interactive and engaging instructional approaches.

KEYWORDS: Gamified vocabulary instruction, learning motivation, vocabulary learning, young learners, Vietnam

1. INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary is a fundamental component of language acquisition, enabling learners to comprehend texts, express ideas, and engage in meaningful communication. In EFL contexts, particularly among young learners aged 11–13, vocabulary learning plays a crucial role in building linguistic confidence and sustaining interest in learning English. However, vocabulary instruction in many classrooms has traditionally relied on rote memorization, mechanical drills, and teacher-centered practices, which often result in low engagement, reduced motivation, and limited long-term retention.

To overcome these limitations, researchers and educators have increasingly explored gamification as an innovative instructional approach. Defined as the use of game design elements in non-game contexts (Deterding et al., 2011), gamification aims to enhance motivation and engagement by incorporating features such as rewards, challenges, feedback, and competition. A growing body of international research (e.g., Hamari et al., 2014; Jaiswal, 2024; Sadeghi et al., 2022) has shown that gamified learning activities can encourage active participation and sustained effort, thereby positively influencing learners' motivation.

In the Vietnamese context, recent studies (e.g., Nguyen, 2021; Le & Pham, 2023) have also indicated the potential of gamification to enhance motivation and engagement in English vocabulary learning, particularly among young learners. Nevertheless, most existing research has been conducted in major urban areas such as Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City, where educational resources and technological infrastructure are more readily available. As a result, there remains a lack of empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of gamified instruction in provincial settings.

Addressing this gap, the present study investigates the impact of gamified vocabulary instruction on the motivation of young learners at a foreign language center in Ca Mau, a less-studied provincial context in Vietnam. By examining learners' motivational responses and perceptions of gamified activities, the study seeks to contribute to the growing literature on gamification in EFL education and to offer practical pedagogical insights for improving vocabulary instruction in similar contexts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Motivation in Language Learning

Motivation has long been recognized as a key determinant of success in second and foreign language learning, as it influences learners' initiation, persistence, and intensity of effort throughout the learning process. Gardner (1985) conceptualized motivation as a combination of effort, desire, and positive attitudes toward the target language, while Dörnyei (2001) emphasized its role in learners' engagement, perseverance, and sustained commitment to language learning.

Over time, theories of language learning motivation have shifted from behaviorist views, which emphasized external reinforcement such as rewards and grades, to more cognitively and socially oriented perspectives. Among these, Self-Determination Theory (SDT) proposed by Deci and Ryan (1985) has been particularly influential. SDT highlights intrinsic motivation, learning driven by interest, enjoyment, and personal satisfaction, and argues that motivation is enhanced when learners' needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are satisfied. In language classrooms, opportunities for choice, experiences of success, and supportive social interactions have been shown to foster higher levels of motivation (Noels, 2001).

Motivation is also dynamic and context-dependent rather than a stable individual trait. Dörnyei's (2009) L2 Motivational Self System further explains how learners' self-concepts and classroom experiences shape their motivation. The system comprises the Ideal L2 Self, the Ought-to L2 Self, and the L2 Learning Experience, with the latter, particularly engaging and interactive classroom activities playing a crucial role in sustaining motivation, especially among young learners.

For young EFL learners, motivation is often fragile due to limited attention spans and a strong preference for enjoyable and hands-on learning experiences. Traditional teacher-centered approaches, such as rote memorization and mechanical repetition, are therefore less effective in maintaining engagement. Previous research (Brewster et al., 2002) indicates that young learners benefit most from lessons that are playful, meaningful, and connected to real-life contexts. Consequently, pedagogical strategies that promote intrinsic motivation, including games, songs, and interactive technologies, are essential for sustaining learner engagement.

Within this theoretical framework, gamification has emerged as a promising instructional approach that enhances motivation by transforming conventional learning activities into engaging, goal-oriented experiences. By addressing learners' psychological needs as outlined in SDT and facilitating states of "flow" (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990), gamification offers a strong theoretical basis for understanding how motivation can be effectively fostered in young learners' vocabulary learning.

2.2. Gamification in Language Education

Gamification has emerged as a pedagogical innovation that integrates game elements into non-game contexts, including education (Deterding et al., 2011). In language education, gamification refers to the intentional use of features such as points, badges, leaderboards, levels, and rewards to enhance learner motivation and engagement. Unlike educational games, which are fully game-based systems, gamification embeds game-like mechanics into conventional instructional activities, thereby making learning more interactive without fundamentally altering curricular content.

The theoretical foundation of gamification is closely linked to motivational psychology, particularly Self-Determination Theory (SDT) proposed by Deci and Ryan (1985). SDT distinguishes between intrinsic motivation, driven by interest and enjoyment, and extrinsic motivation, influenced by external incentives. Gamified learning environments can support both forms of motivation by providing enjoyable learning experiences while offering external rewards. More importantly, gamification seeks to satisfy learners' basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness through choice, feedback, progress tracking, and social interaction.

Flow Theory (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990) further explains the motivational potential of gamification. When learning tasks are appropriately designed to balance challenge and skill, set clear goals, and provide immediate feedback, learners are more likely to experience a state of flow characterized by deep concentration and enjoyment. In language learning contexts, such flow experiences can sustain attention, enhance engagement, and promote long-term motivation.

Empirical studies have consistently supported the positive effects of gamification in educational settings. A meta-analysis by Hamari et al. (2014) reported that gamified environments generally improved learner engagement and learning outcomes. In language education, recent studies have shown that gamified platforms such as Quizizz increased students' participation, enjoyment, and motivation compared to traditional instruction (Jaiswal, 2024; Le & Pham, 2023).

Nevertheless, the effectiveness of gamification largely depends on instructional design and contextual appropriateness. Overemphasis on extrinsic rewards without meaningful learning objectives may result in superficial engagement or undermine

intrinsic motivation (Sadeghi et al., 2022). Therefore, gamification should be implemented strategically as a supportive pedagogical tool rather than a substitute for sound teaching practices.

In the Vietnamese EFL context, gamification has attracted increasing attention as a response to the limitations of traditional, teacher-centered instruction. However, existing research has primarily focused on urban educational settings, leaving a gap in understanding its application in provincial areas such as Ca Mau. Exploring the impact of gamified vocabulary instruction on young learners' motivation in such contexts can provide valuable insights into both the theoretical and practical dimensions of gamification in language education.

2.3. Gamified Vocabulary Instruction

Gamified vocabulary instruction refers to the purposeful integration of game design elements into vocabulary teaching in order to enhance learners' motivation, engagement, and participation. Unlike entertainment-oriented games, gamified instruction preserves instructional objectives while incorporating features such as points, rewards, levels, competition, collaboration, and immediate feedback to make vocabulary learning more interactive and enjoyable (Deterding et al., 2011; Sailer et al., 2017). Traditional vocabulary instruction in EFL classrooms has often relied on rote memorization, mechanical drills, and translation-focused practices, which may support short-term recall but frequently fail to sustain motivation among young learners aged 11–13 (Nation, 2013). Gamification addresses these limitations by transforming vocabulary practice into playful and meaningful repeated interaction with target words, thereby enhancing both motivation and retention.

Consistent with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985), the gamified activities were designed to satisfy learners' needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness through achievable challenges, choice, immediate feedback, and peer interaction. Previous studies have shown that such gamified vocabulary activities can enhance young learners' motivation, enjoyment, and vocabulary retention (Hamari et al., 2014; Jaiswal, 2024; Cortez Erraez et al., 2025). At the same time, the study adopted a varied range of game formats to avoid over-competition and monotony, responding to concerns that poorly designed gamification may reduce intrinsic motivation (Sadeghi et al., 2022).

2.4 Previous Studies on Gamified Vocabulary Teaching

2.4.1 Studies in the world

A growing body of international research has examined the effectiveness of gamification in enhancing learners' motivation and engagement in English vocabulary learning. Overall, these studies suggest that well-designed gamified instruction can make vocabulary learning more interactive and appealing, thereby sustaining learners' interest.

Experimental research by Jaiswal (2024) demonstrated that university students exposed to gamified vocabulary instruction via Kahoot showed significantly higher levels of motivation, concentration, and learning satisfaction than those receiving traditional instruction. Similarly, Cortez Erraez et al. (2025) reported that the use of points, badges, and leaderboards increased young learners' participation and facilitated more natural vocabulary use through repeated exposure. Supporting these findings, Hamari et al.'s (2014) systematic review concluded that gamification generally enhances motivation and engagement when game elements are meaningfully aligned with learning objectives.

However, international findings are not entirely consistent. Some studies (e.g., Sadeghi et al., 2022; Hanus & Fox, 2015) found that while gamification improved enjoyment and motivation, its effects on long-term learning outcomes were limited. These mixed results highlight the importance of instructional design quality, duration of intervention, and contextual suitability in determining the effectiveness of gamified learning.

Overall, international studies confirm the motivational potential of gamification in EFL contexts, while also emphasizing the need for thoughtful implementation to avoid superficial engagement.

2.4.2 Studies in Vietnam

In Vietnam, research on gamification and game-based vocabulary instruction has gradually increased across different educational levels. Existing studies generally report positive effects on learner engagement, motivation, and classroom atmosphere through the use of digital platforms and physical games.

At the tertiary level, Pham and Duong (2022) found that Kahoot-based vocabulary instruction enhanced student interaction and short-term retention. Research involving younger learners also reported favorable outcomes. Le and Pham (2023) observed increased participation and confidence among learners aged 10–13 in private language centers, while Nguyen (2021) showed that students

taught through vocabulary games outperformed those taught using traditional methods. From a pedagogical perspective, Ngoc (2021) reported that Vietnamese EFL teachers held positive attitudes toward gamification, though they faced constraints related to technology access and classroom management.

Despite these encouraging findings, Vietnamese studies are often small-scale, conducted mainly in urban areas, and rely on descriptive or quasi-experimental designs. Evidence regarding sustained motivational change, learners' perceptions, and implementation in provincial contexts remains limited.

2.5. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study integrates motivational theories and gamification principles to explain how gamified vocabulary instruction influences young learners' motivation in EFL contexts. It is grounded in Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985), Flow Theory (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990), and gamification principles proposed by Deterding et al. (2011).

According to Self-Determination Theory, intrinsic motivation is enhanced when learners' needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are satisfied. In gamified vocabulary instruction, autonomy is supported through choice and interactive participation; competence is fostered through immediate feedback, achievable challenges, and visible progress; and relatedness is promoted through collaboration and peer interaction. These elements are particularly influential for learners aged 11–13, whose motivation is highly sensitive to classroom dynamics.

Flow Theory further explains how gamified tasks can generate deep engagement when challenge and skill are balanced, goals are clear, and feedback is immediate. Such conditions encourage sustained concentration, enjoyment, and persistence in vocabulary learning.

Within this framework, Gamified Vocabulary Instruction is positioned as the independent variable, encompassing game elements such as points, rewards, competition, collaboration, and movement-based activities. Learners' Motivation is the dependent variable, conceptualized through three dimensions: enjoyment, effort, and perceived usefulness. Learners' Perception functions as a mediating factor, influencing the extent to which gamified instruction enhances motivation.

Overall, this framework provides a coherent theoretical basis for examining how gamification shapes young learners' motivation and perceptions in vocabulary learning, guiding both data collection and analysis in the present study.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Context

This study was conducted at Hai Au Star English Center, a private multi-branch institution in Ca Mau City that offers Cambridge-based English programs for children and teenagers. Similar to many provincial language centers, vocabulary teaching has traditionally relied on textbook-driven repetition, translation, and memorization, which may support short-term recall but often fails to sustain motivation (Nation, 2001; Schmitt, 2008). In response to learner disengagement and the national shift toward learner-centered instruction (MOET, 2018), the center has begun experimenting with interactive and gamified activities; however, evidence of effectiveness in provincial contexts remains limited. The study targeted learners aged 11–13, a group that benefits from playful, competitive learning while developing increasing cognitive capacity for language study (Cameron, 2001; Piaget, 1972). Over a ten-week term, gamified activities were integrated into vocabulary lessons to examine their influence on learner motivation.

3.2 Research Design and Approach

A convergent mixed-methods design was adopted to investigate the effects of gamified vocabulary instruction on young learners' motivation. Quantitative data were collected through a post-intervention questionnaire, while qualitative data were obtained from semi-structured interviews and classroom observations. The ten-week intervention incorporated both cognitive-based and movement-based gamified tasks (e.g., Bingo, Quizizz, crosswords, matching, writing races, memory games, station challenges) aligned with the Cambridge-based syllabus to ensure that gamification supported instructional objectives rather than replacing content.

3.3 Participants and Sampling

3.3.1 Student Participants

Fifty EFL learners aged 11–13 participated in the study. All were at elementary level based on the center's placement test and attended two 90-minute lessons per week. Convenience sampling was used due to accessibility at the research site, while purposive

criteria (age, consistent attendance, willingness to participate) ensured relevance to the study's objectives. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from both students and parents.

3.3.2 Teacher Participants

Four teachers were involved in the implementation process. One teacher delivered the intervention, while two teachers (excluding the researcher) participated in post-intervention interviews to provide professional perspectives on learner motivation and implementation challenges. Additional teacher input was used to support triangulation.

3.3.3 Research Site

Hai Au Star English Center operates across multiple locations in Ca Mau and provides small-class instruction (typically 10–15 learners). This environment is conducive to interactive activities and allows close monitoring of learner engagement during gamified lessons.

3.4 Research Instruments

3.4.1 Gamified Vocabulary Activities

The intervention served as the primary instructional tool and included cognitive-based games (e.g., Bingo, Quizizz, Word Search, Crossword, Matching, Memory Game, Hot Seat, Writing Race) and movement-based games (e.g., Station Race, Musical Chairs, Pass the Ball, Pass the Obstacle). Activities were adapted to learners' age and proficiency and aligned with weekly curriculum objectives.

3.4.2 Student Questionnaire

A 20-item Likert-scale questionnaire (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) was administered after the intervention to measure learners' motivational responses and perceptions. The instrument covered three domains: (A) interest/engagement, (B) perceived learning effectiveness, and (C) willingness to continue learning through games. The questionnaire was translated into Vietnamese, reviewed by EFL teachers for clarity, piloted with 10 non-participating learners, and revised accordingly (Appendix B).

3.4.3 Student Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with approximately ten students to explore their experiences with gamified lessons, focusing on comparisons with traditional instruction and perceived motivational changes. Interviews were conducted in Vietnamese, audio-recorded with consent, transcribed, translated into English, and analyzed thematically.

3.4.4 Teacher Interviews

Two teachers (excluding the researcher) participated in semi-structured interviews focusing on observed changes in learner motivation and practical challenges in implementing gamified vocabulary activities. Interviews were conducted in Vietnamese, recorded with consent, transcribed, and analyzed thematically.

3.5 Data Collection Procedures

Data collection consisted of three phases. First, permission was obtained from the center, and consent forms were distributed to parents and students. Instruments were validated by teacher review and piloting. Second, the ten-week intervention was implemented within regular classes, with varied gamified tasks integrated into vocabulary lessons. Classroom observations were conducted throughout to document learner engagement and interaction. Third, at the end of the intervention, students completed the questionnaire, followed by student and teacher interviews. All datasets were coded and organized for analysis.

3.6 Data Analysis

3.6.1 Quantitative Analysis

Questionnaire data were coded (1–5) and analyzed using SPSS. Internal consistency was examined using Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha \geq .70$). Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies) were used to summarize motivational patterns. Where appropriate, basic inferential tests (e.g., t-tests/ANOVA) were used to explore subgroup differences.

3.6.2 Qualitative Analysis

Interview transcripts and observation notes were analyzed thematically following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase procedure. Coding focused on motivational patterns (e.g., enjoyment, effort, engagement, perceived usefulness), perceptions of game elements, and implementation constraints. Representative quotations were used to support interpretations.

3.6.3 Triangulation

Triangulation was conducted by comparing questionnaire results with interview themes and observation notes. Convergent and divergent patterns were examined during interpretation to enhance credibility and provide a comprehensive account of motivational change (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

3.7 Reliability and Validity

Questionnaire reliability was supported through piloting, Cronbach's alpha, and standardized administration procedures. Validity was strengthened through expert review, alignment with motivational theory (e.g., SDT), clear construct mapping across questionnaire domains, and triangulation of quantitative and qualitative evidence. For qualitative data, credibility was enhanced through systematic coding, documentation of analytic decisions, and cross-checking of themes where feasible.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles were strictly followed. Written consent was obtained from the center, parents, teachers, and students. Participation was voluntary, confidentiality and anonymity were ensured through coded identifiers, and participants could withdraw at any stage without consequences. Data were securely stored and reported in aggregated form. The study followed institutional and APA ethical guidelines for research involving minors.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Overview of Findings

This section presents and discusses findings from four data sources: (1) a post-intervention questionnaire administered to 50 students, (2) semi-structured interviews with ten students, (3) interviews with two English teachers, and (4) classroom observation notes collected during the ten-week intervention. The mixed-methods analysis aims to address the two research questions concerning learners' perceptions of gamified vocabulary instruction and its impact on their motivation.

Quantitative data provide an overall profile of students' motivational responses following the intervention, while qualitative data offer deeper insights into learners' emotional engagement, classroom behavior, and perceptions of gamified activities. Triangulating these sources allows for a comprehensive understanding of how gamified vocabulary instruction influenced young EFL learners aged 11–13 in a provincial context.

4.2 Reliability of the Questionnaire

Reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha indicated satisfactory internal consistency across all three motivational dimensions. The Enjoyment scale achieved an alpha of 0.835, the Effort scale yielded 0.785, and the Perceived Usefulness scale recorded the highest reliability at 0.862. All values exceeded the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70, and corrected item–total correlations were above 0.30. These results confirm that the questionnaire reliably measured learners' motivation and was suitable for further analysis.

4.3 Quantitative Findings

4.3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive analysis of the 20 questionnaire items revealed generally positive learner responses to gamified vocabulary instruction. Mean scores across items ranged from 3.86 to 4.58 on a five-point Likert scale, with relatively low standard deviations, indicating shared positive perceptions among participants.

At the dimension level, Enjoyment and Effort recorded the highest mean scores (both $M = 4.31$), followed by Perceived Usefulness ($M = 4.14$). The Overall Motivation index reached a high level ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.55$), suggesting that learners felt motivated, engaged, and positive after participating in the gamified lessons.

4.3.2 Interpretation

The high enjoyment scores indicate that gamified activities successfully created a positive emotional learning environment. Students reported feeling happier, more relaxed, and more interested during vocabulary lessons with games. Effort-related results show that learners actively participated and invested energy in completing tasks, likely due to competitive elements, teamwork, and immediate feedback. Although Perceived Usefulness scored slightly lower, learners still strongly agreed that gamified activities supported vocabulary understanding, recall, and confidence.

Overall, the quantitative findings demonstrate that gamified vocabulary instruction positively influenced multiple dimensions of motivation among young EFL learners.

4.4 Qualitative Findings

4.4.1 Student Interviews

Analysis of student interviews revealed two main themes. First, learners experienced positive emotional engagement through playful learning. Students described gamified lessons as “fun,” “exciting,” and “less boring” than traditional vocabulary learning, which reduced anxiety and encouraged participation.

Second, students reported increased motivation and willingness to learn. Competition, rewards, and teamwork motivated them to concentrate, remember vocabulary more quickly, and try harder during lessons. Even when losing a game, learners expressed a desire to continue playing, indicating sustained motivation rather than discouragement.

4.4.2 Teacher Interviews

Teacher interviews confirmed noticeable improvements in learner engagement and classroom atmosphere. Teachers observed higher participation levels, increased confidence among quieter students, and greater enthusiasm during gamified lessons. However, they also reported challenges related to time management, classroom control, and the need to adapt games to learners’ age and maturity. Movement-based games, in particular, required careful supervision to ensure safety and maintain focus.

4.4.3 Integration of Qualitative Findings

Triangulating student and teacher perspectives reveals consistent evidence that gamified vocabulary instruction enhanced motivation, enjoyment, and participation. While both groups acknowledged implementation challenges, they agreed that thoughtfully designed gamified activities transformed vocabulary lessons into more engaging and meaningful learning experiences.

4.5 Discussion

4.5.1 Learners’ Perceptions of Gamified Vocabulary Instruction

Learners generally perceived gamified vocabulary instruction as enjoyable, motivating, and more effective than traditional methods. The use of games satisfied key motivational needs related to autonomy, competence, and relatedness, supporting Self-Determination Theory. Students felt more confident, socially connected, and willing to participate, which aligns with motivational teaching principles in EFL contexts.

4.5.2 Extent of Motivation Enhancement

Although the study did not employ a pre-test design, the consistently high post-intervention mean scores suggest a strong motivational impact of gamified instruction. Enjoyment and effort were particularly pronounced, indicating that emotional engagement and active participation were key outcomes. Learners’ perceptions of usefulness further suggest that gamification supported meaningful vocabulary learning, not merely entertainment.

4.5.3 Comparison with Previous Studies

The findings align with international and Vietnamese research showing that gamification enhances motivation and engagement in vocabulary learning. Consistent with previous studies, the results also highlight that the effectiveness of gamification depends on thoughtful design, appropriate challenge levels, and pedagogical alignment. The present study extends existing research by providing evidence from a provincial Vietnamese context involving young learners aged 11–13.

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study provides empirical evidence that integrating gamified elements into vocabulary instruction positively influences young learners’ motivation in EFL contexts. Gamification increased enjoyment and effort, fostered positive emotional engagement, and enhanced learners’ perceptions of the usefulness of vocabulary learning. Interactive and competitive features sustained attention and encouraged active participation.

Pedagogically, the findings confirm that gamification is an effective motivational strategy for young learners when balanced with clear learning goals. Successful implementation requires careful activity design, appropriate difficulty levels, and effective classroom management to ensure that games support learning rather than distract from it. In sum, gamified vocabulary instruction represents a valuable approach for creating engaging and motivating EFL learning environments, particularly in provincial contexts.

5.2 Pedagogical Implications

Several pedagogical implications emerge from the study. First, teachers are encouraged to integrate simple gamified elements such as points, challenges, teamwork, and feedback into vocabulary lessons to increase enjoyment and participation. Second, clear rules,

time limits, and safety considerations are essential, especially for movement-based activities, to maintain focus and prevent disruption. Third, gamification should be used as a means to support learning outcomes; post-game reinforcement activities are necessary to consolidate vocabulary knowledge. Finally, language centers should provide professional development and resources to support teachers in designing and implementing effective gamified instruction that accommodates diverse learner preferences.

5.3 Recommendations for Future Research

Future studies should involve larger and more diverse samples across multiple institutions to enhance generalizability. Longitudinal designs are recommended to examine the sustainability of motivational effects and vocabulary retention. Incorporating objective learning measures (e.g., pre- and post-tests) would clarify the relationship between motivation and learning gains. Further research could also compare different gamification designs and explore teachers' implementation strategies in greater depth using mixed-methods approaches.

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